

D2.2

HUB Terms of References

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
BG	Bulgaria
DX.X	Deliverable X.X
CEE	Central and Eastern Europe
CET	Communication Expert Team
CZ	Czechia
EE	Estonia
HCB	HUB Coordination Body
HR	Croatia
HU	Hungary
LV	Latvia
LT	Lithuania
NMG	National Mirror Group
NPC	National Contact Point
PL	Poland
QH	Quadruple Helix (government, industry, academia, and the public)
R&I	Research and Innovation
RO	Romania
SI	Slovenia
SK	Slovakia
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
ToR	Terms of Reference
TWG	Thematic Working Group
WP	Work Package

Introduction to the project

BOOST4BIOEAST is a Coordination and Support Action funded by the European Commission developed to support the BIOEAST Initiative with the aim of empowering national stakeholders in the Central Eastern European and Baltic countries for the development of national bioeconomy action plans and to build long-lasting structures and spaces of dialogue for national and macro-regional cooperation. The project will enrich knowledge on the bioeconomy and stimulate related research and innovation across the macro-region.

Executive Summary

This report provides a comprehensive comparison of the Terms of References (ToRs) of 10 **national BIOEAST HUBs** developed under the **BOOST4BIOEAST** project. These HUBs—based in Bulgaria, Croatia, Czechia, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Romania, Slovakia, and Slovenia—represent key national platforms for promoting sustainable and circular bioeconomy development in the BIOEAST macro-region. Each HUB serves to connect national stakeholders, support policy design, and contribute to EU-wide bioeconomy dialogues. This comparative report analyses the ToRs across four core dimensions: objectives, organization and governance, internal structure, and core activities.

Most ToRs were developed with BOOST4BIOEAST support, though the Czech ToR predate the project and exhibit more limited alignment with the theoretical framework established in the **BIOEAST HUB Handbook** (Deliverable 2.1).

The analysis reveals broad alignment across HUBs in terms of strategic direction and mission. All ToRs emphasize multi-stakeholder collaboration, policy engagement, and the promotion of research and innovation. Governance models vary, from structured HUBs with formal membership and decision-making bodies to more open networks focused on inclusive participation. Common operational structures include Coordination Teams, **National Mirror Groups** (NMGs), and alignment with the BIOEAST Initiative's macro-regional **Thematic Working Groups** (TWGs). Activities focus on facilitating policy dialogue, building national capacity, fostering innovation, and disseminating bioeconomy knowledge.

Key challenges include gaps in formal governance and decision-making mechanisms, varying maturity of stakeholder engagement strategies, and inconsistent links to macro-regional structures. Recommendations include harmonizing HUB structures, enhancing cross-border cooperation, developing joint TWG-NMG strategies, and ensuring timely updates of all ToRs.

1 Introduction

The **BIOEAST Initiative**, launched by 11 Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries, aims to ensure the sustainable development of the bioeconomy in the macro-region, addressing specific challenges of agriculture, forestry, and rural areas. The Initiative's activities are driven by its 7 TWGs, macro-regional expert groups from policy and research side, focusing on priority bioeconomy themes (agroecology, bioenergy, biomaterials, food systems, forestry, freshwater, education).

The **BOOST4BIOEAST** project supports the development and consolidation of **national BIOEAST HUBs**, which are critical enablers of sustainable and circular bioeconomy transitions across the BIOEAST macro-region. These HUBs serve as national platforms for fostering cooperation among stakeholders and promoting the development of evidence-based bioeconomy policies. The HUBs consist of NMGs, as thematic bodies, reflecting the structure and topics of the macro-regional TWGs, to ensure national-level input and alignment.

Prior to setting up the HUBs, under the framework of BOOST4BIOEAST, existing networks, relevant actors, and resources were mapped, previous HUB experiences were reviewed, guidelines for national stakeholder engagement strategies were developed, and a common set of activities was determined. These methodological approaches and the proposed portfolio of activities were gathered in the **BIOEAST HUB Handbook** (D2.1), providing a theoretical framework for creating and operating the HUBs.

Subsequently, 9 national bioeconomy HUBs were newly established, accompanied by the invigoration of 2 already existing ones, overseen by a HUB Coordination Body (HCB) monitoring the process and serving as a forum for HUB Coordinators to exchange peer experiences. An essential step in setting up the HUBs was the development of ToR documents together with quadruple helix stakeholders and based on the methods, guidelines, and recommendations outlined in the BIOEAST HUB Handbook. Each ToR details the objectives; priorities, initial portfolio of activities, basic internal rules and procedures of the respective HUB, including the creation and integration of NMGs. The documents were validated at national HUB kick-off workshops by the participating national stakeholders.

This deliverable (D2.2) seeks to provide a **structured comparison** of the final ToR documents of ten HUBs to assess alignment with BIOEAST strategic goals and identify opportunities for improvement. It offers valuable insights and practical benefits to the BOOST4BIOEAST consortium by providing a baseline for monitoring HUB development, as well as an opportunity for mutual learning and harmonisation of HUB governance, structure, and activities across member countries. Based on this analysis, HUB coordination teams can identify missing elements in their own ToRs, strive for closer alignment with the BIOEAST framework, and revise governance structures or activity plans based on peer examples.

In the following chapters, the **methodology** of the assessment is explained first. This is followed by the **comparative analysis** of all HUB ToR documents (Chapter 3). **Gaps and common challenges** are highlighted in Chapter 4, followed by the **conclusions and recommendations** for future refinement of the documents (Chapter 5) to ensure compliance with BOOST4BIOEAST and that HUB activities better support the long-term objectives of the BIOEAST Initiative.

2 Scope and Methodology

This report reviews the ToRs of 10 BIOEAST HUBs—Bulgaria, Croatia, Czechia, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Romania, Slovakia, and Slovenia. The Polish HUB's ToR was not available at the time of writing.

The comparative analysis of the ToRs follows a section-by-section approach, drawing from the conceptual framework in the BIOEAST HUB Handbook. Each document was assessed with respect to four key areas:

Objectives: The strategic aims expressed in each HUB's ToR, including goals related to national bioeconomy development, stakeholder integration, and alignment with EU strategies.

Organization & Governance: Coordination, leadership, decision-making procedures, and stakeholder engagement rules outlined in the HUBs' ToRs.

Structure: The internal configuration of the HUB, including coordination teams, thematic NMGs, and their connection to the international TWGs.

Activities: The range of operations undertaken by the HUBs, including stakeholder meetings, capacity-building events, policy workshops, dissemination, and project engagement.

All ToRs were reviewed using the above categories and were thus assessed for alignment with the BIOEAST HUB Handbook. Key features such as formalization level, inclusiveness, sectoral representation, and resource support were considered. Cross-comparison allowed for the identification of common models, innovative practices, and areas requiring further harmonization and improvement.

This uniform approach enables:

Comparability across member countries: With 11 national HUBs developed under different conditions, a standardized framework was essential to ensure consistency in analysis and allow side-by-side comparisons.

Assess alignment with the HUB Handbook: The categories reflect the conceptual structure introduced in the BIOEAST HUB Handbook, ensuring coherence with the project's theoretical and strategic foundation.

Clarity for stakeholders: By organizing the review around key functional areas, the assessment allows HUB coordination teams and stakeholders to quickly understand the strengths and gaps in each ToR, supporting monitoring and future updates.

The following paragraphs (**Chapter 3**) present detailed HUB-by-HUB comparisons under these categories. Each section includes a structured narrative synthesis followed by a comparative table summarizing the key features across all HUBs.

3 Comparative Analysis of HUB Terms of References

3.1 Objectives

The objectives articulated across the HUB ToRs show a strong alignment with the overarching vision of the BIOEAST Initiative, while also reflecting each country's specific priorities and institutional context. In general, HUB objectives can be categorized into four broad groups: **(1)** supporting the development of national bioeconomy strategies and policies; **(2)** fostering stakeholder dialogue and engagement; **(3)** enhancing research, education, and innovation; and **(4)** ensuring alignment with EU and international frameworks.

HUBs such as those in Croatia, Hungary, Latvia, and Romania place significant emphasis on **supporting policy development** and aligning national strategies with EU policy frameworks. Hungary, for example, identifies the HUB as a key enabler for national strategy implementation through evidence-based policy support and stakeholder coordination. HUBs, in general, define themselves as policy support instruments directly linked to national government strategies and inter-ministerial collaboration.

In contrast, HUBs like those in Estonia and Lithuania place more focus on inclusivity and promoting open **stakeholder dialogue and cooperation**. Their objectives stress participatory processes, bottom-up coordination, and enhancing awareness about bioeconomy transitions across diverse stakeholder groups. Such objectives, to varying degrees, are shared among all HUBs.

Research and innovation (R&I) also feature prominently in several HUB objectives. The Croatian and Bulgarian HUBs, for instance, aim to stimulate interdisciplinary research collaboration, support education, and facilitate access to innovation funding.

Reflecting the early stages of HUB creation, some ToR documents put considerable emphasis on setting up and **developing the HUB organisation** itself. This is particularly well highlighted by the Bulgarian HUB but also listed among primary objectives in the case of Estonia.

The Czech ToR, developed outside the BOOST4BIOEAST framework, expresses similar strategic objectives but often in more general terms. Their document suggests a desire for policy integration and multi-sector engagement but provide less detail regarding alignment with the BIOEAST TWGs or NMGs.

Overall, all ToRs reflect the core aim of the HUB concept: to act as national platforms supporting sustainable, inclusive, and evidence-based bioeconomy transitions. Variations in emphasis largely stem from differences in national priorities, policy maturity, stakeholder ecosystems, and institutional arrangements.

Table 1: Objectives of BIOEAST HUBs

Country	Key Objectives
Bulgaria	build HUB organisation ; facilitate stakeholder engagement; support policy development; foster bioeconomy solutions; encourage dialogue and cooperation
Croatia	facilitate stakeholder engagement; support policy development & implementation ; foster inter-ministerial cooperation; promote research and innovation; encourage dialogue and cooperation
Czechia	facilitate stakeholder engagement & knowledge exchange ; support policy development; promote R&I; foster inter-ministerial cooperation; boost communication & dissemination; support National Contact Points (NCPs)
Estonia	build HUB organisation; facilitate stakeholder engagement; support policy development; promote stakeholder-driven initiatives; encourage dialogue and cooperation
Hungary	facilitate stakeholder engagement; support policy development & implementation ; foster inter-ministerial cooperation; promote R&I; encourage dialogue and cooperation
Latvia	support policy development ; promote R&I; encourage dialogue and cooperation
Lithuania	support policy development; foster inter-ministerial cooperation; encourage dialogue and cooperation ; cooperate with BIOEAST at macro-regional level
Romania	facilitate stakeholder engagement; support policy development & implementation ; promote R&I; encourage dialogue and cooperation
Slovakia	facilitate stakeholder engagement; support policy development; encourage dialogue and cooperation ; foster capacity building; boost communication & dissemination; foster bioeconomy projects
Slovenia	facilitate stakeholder engagement; promote R&I and knowledge exchange; foster capacity building; encourage dialogue, cooperation & knowledge exchange

source: own compilation based on HUB ToRs (ToR BG-SI, n.d.)

3.2 Organisation & Governance

The governance arrangements of the BIOEAST HUBs reveal a spectrum of approaches ranging from formal, structured coordination bodies to more open and informal arrangements. While all HUBs designate a coordinating institution or a consortium of multiple entities, the internal decision-making structures and levels of formality vary significantly.

HUBs in Bulgaria, Croatia, Hungary, Romania, and Slovenia exhibit highly structured governance systems. These HUBs have established formal **Coordination Teams** with defined roles, responsibilities, and meeting procedures. The Coordination Team is generally supported by NMG leaders. Decision-making is based on consensus, but the Coordinator is the ultimate authority in most cases. A notable exception is the Latvian HUB, where decisions made by the Coordination Team can be overruled by the president of the university leading the organisation.

Figure 1. Organisational structures of the a) Croatian, b) Estonian, c) Hungarian, and d) Lithuanian BIOEAST HUBs. (source: ToR BG-SI, n.d.)

In addition, HUBs such as those in Latvia and Estonia emphasize **openness and flexibility** in governance. They maintain informal coordination teams and allow for dynamic participation without strict membership procedures. These HUBs prioritize inclusiveness and aim to mobilize a broad range of actors by reducing administrative barriers. A similar but quite unique

approach is that of Slovenia: the HUB here is led by a Coordination Committee, in which all institutional members are represented, along with the Coordination Team, the national BIOEAST NCP, and the inter-ministerial working group.

Across HUBs, coordination is typically anchored by academic or research institutions, often with support from relevant ministries or governmental bodies. Most ToRs outline at least basic rules for stakeholder engagement, though only some provide operational details such as voting procedures or term limits for coordinators.

Some HUB Coordination Teams are supported by a dedicated **Communication Expert Team** (CET) that is also responsible for liaising with the respective Work Package (WP8) of the BOOST4BIOEAST project. Notable exceptions in this regard are Czechia, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, and Slovakia, where the setting up of such a unit is strongly recommended.

Most HUBs opted for an open and **informal membership** model. Several organisations (Croatia, Lithuania, Romania, Slovenia), however, emphasize that membership could be formalised in the future. Hungary goes even further, seeking to formalise the status of their members already. Joining the HUBs is generally handled at the NMG level, with the ultimate decision made by the Coordinator.

Practically all HUBs employ the same **conflict resolution** procedures, with informal discussions preferred at first, followed by the formal involvement of the Coordinator. The ultimate forum for resolving disputes is the BIOEAST Board, the highest decision-making body of the BIOEAST Initiative. The one exception is that of the Latvian HUB that prefers informal discussion and reconciliation in all disputes.

The Czech HUB, due to their earlier development, have less detailed governance descriptions. While they identify national coordinators and general coordination mechanisms, their ToR lacks specific procedural detail or governance roles. This limits their alignment with the comprehensive framework promoted by BOOST4BIOEAST. Unfortunately, the ToR of the Slovak HUB is also lacking and reveals very little information in this regard. These shortcomings are strongly encouraged to be resolved in the future.

Table 2. Governance of BIOEAST HUBs

Country	Coordinating Institutions	Governance Structure	Membership Rules	Decision-Making	Conflict resolution
Bulgaria	Agricultural Academy	Coordination Team + NMG leaders + CET (not specified)	open, informal / NMGs decide	Coordinator / voting initiated by coordinator	informal / HUB Coordinator / BIOEAST Board
Croatia	Energy Institute Hrvoje Požar; University of Zagreb; Croatian Chamber of Agriculture	Coordination Team + NMG leaders + CET	open, informal / possibly formalised in future	Coordinator / NMG leaders / consensus	informal / HUB Coordinator / BIOEAST Board
Czechia	BIOEAST HUB CR (legal entity); Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic	not specified	not specified	not specified	not specified
Estonia	Estonian University of Life Sciences	Coordination Team + NMG leaders	open, informal / NMGs decide	Coordinator / voting initiated by coordinator	informal / HUB Coordinator / BIOEAST Board
Hungary	Budapest University of Technology and Economics; HUN-REN Research Centre for Natural Sciences; Institute of Agricultural Economics	Coordination Team + NMG leaders + CET	open, formal / NMGs decide	Coordinator / NMG leaders / consensus	informal / HUB Coordinator / BIOEAST Board
Latvia	Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies	Coordination Team	open, informal , voluntary	Coordination Team / university rector	informal discussion and reconciliation

Table 2. Governance of BIOEAST HUBs (continued)

Country	Coordinating Institutions	Governance Structure	Membership Rules	Decision-Making	Conflict resolution
Lithuania	Vytautas Magnus University Agriculture Academy	Coordination Committee (coord. + institutional members)	open, informal / possibly formalised in future	Coordinator / NMG leaders / consensus based on wide representation	informal / HUB Coordinator / BIOEAST Board
Romania	Research Institute for Agriculture Economy and Rural Development; Academy of Agricultural and Forestry Sciences; Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development	Coordination Team + NMG leaders + CET	open, informal / possibly formalised in future	Coordinator / NMG leaders / consensus	informal / HUB Coordinator / BIOEAST Board
Slovakia	not specified	not specified	not specified	not specified	not specified
Slovenia	Circular Change; Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food; Chamber of Economy; Anteja ECG	Coordination Team + NMG leaders + CET	open, informal / possibly formalised in future	Coord. Team / NMG leaders / consensus	informal / HUB Coordinator / BIOEAST Board

source: own compilation based on HUB ToRs (ToR BG-SI, n.d.)

3.3 Structure

The internal structures of the BIOEAST HUBs show both convergence and diversity, reflecting national priorities, institutional arrangements, and levels of formality. A majority of HUBs include clearly defined coordination teams, supported in many cases by NMGs or thematic working groups aligned with the macro-regional BIOEAST TWGs.

As to their **membership**, most HUBs welcome both individuals and institutions in their ranks and specifically refer to the preferred inclusion of all types of Quadruple Helix (QH) stakeholders (government, industry, academia, and society in general). Only individuals are considered in the case of Croatia and Estonia, although it is unclear whether this omission is intentional or not. The type of bioeconomy stakeholders accepted as HUB members are not clearly defined in the case of Czechia and Slovakia.

Membership is almost exclusively organised through the **NMGs**, with the sole exception of Latvia. Due to the importance of such national-level thematic groups in the activities BIOEAST Initiative, as well as in accomplishing BOOST4BIOEAST objectives, addressing this shortcoming quickly is strongly advised. Most HUBs specifically define the NMGs that they intend to prioritize. Such preferences differ considerably, reflecting national priorities. For instance, while Agroecology is emphasized in Hungary, Forestry value chains are more relevant to Lithuania.

Considerable **alignment with macro-regional TWGs** is expected in the operation of NMGs. Accordingly, most ToRs emphasize the importance of such alignment. Nonetheless, while some HUBs, such as Croatia, Czechia, Romania makes notable recommendations for such alignment (e.g., direct participation, adopting topics, and harmonising priorities), plans for setting up direct communication channels and realising alignment efforts in practice are not sufficiently detailed in any of the documents examined. Future amendments should address this shortcoming.

Table 3. Structure of BIOEAST HUBs

Country	Membership	Participation in NMGs	Link to TWGs
Bulgaria	individuals / institutions / networks	yes: not specified	alignment envisaged / not specified
Croatia	individuals / institutions	yes: (planned) <i>Bioenergy, Education, Food Systems, Biomaterials</i>	alignment envisaged / alignment through participation, consultation
Czechia	not specified (bioeconomy stakeholders)	yes: Education, Freshwater, Agroecology, Forestry	alignment envisaged / adopt topics & harmonise priorities
Estonia	individuals (QH experts)	yes: not specified	not specified
Hungary	individuals / institutions / (QH stakeholders)	yes: Agroecology, Biomaterials, Education, Food Systems	alignment envisaged / alignment through participation, consultation
Latvia	individuals / institutions / (QH stakeholders)	not specified	not specified
Lithuania	individuals / institutions / (QH stakeholders)	yes: Food Systems, Forestry, Biomaterials	alignment envisaged / along BOOST4BIOEAST activities
Romania	individuals / institutions / (QH stakeholders)	yes: (planned) Agroecology, Biomaterials, Food Systems, Education	alignment envisaged / alignment through participation, consultation
Slovakia	QH stakeholders	yes: (planned) to be specified	some alignment envisaged / along project activities
Slovenia	individuals / institutions / (QH stakeholders)	yes: (planned) Agroecology, Biomaterials, Food Systems, Forestry	alignment envisaged / not specified

source: own compilation based on HUB ToRs (ToR BG-SI, n.d.)

3.4 Activities

The HUB ToRs outline a diverse but overlapping set of activities intended to promote bioeconomy transitions at national and macro-regional levels. These activities typically fall into five categories: **(1)** stakeholder engagement, **(2)** facilitating cooperation, **(3)** policy support, **(4)** R&I support, and **(5)** capacity building.

Most HUBs organize **stakeholder engagement** through regular BIOEAST-related events, such as workshops, annual bioeconomy conferences, as well as HUB meetings. Beyond this, engagement is envisaged to be driven primarily by the NMGs. The Lithuanian HUB ToR includes a particularly detailed stakeholder engagement strategy, built around inclusivity, clearly communicating values, personalising messages, and opting for interactive tools and events. Their approach could well serve as a model for other HUBs to adapt to their needs.

While ToRs tend to markedly emphasize facilitating **cooperation** among bioeconomy stakeholders, few documents provide sufficient detail as to how this would be achieved in practice. Most HUBs – justifiably – rely on their diverse membership enabling the flow of information among representatives of different sectors and stakeholder groups. Communication and dissemination are also widely recognized as critical in this regard. Most HUBs plan to use newsletters, events, and participation in European-level fora to share findings and promote the bioeconomy narrative. Czechia and Slovakia go one step further, mentioning actively engaging in business discovery efforts to engage new entities, particularly SME and startups. Slovenia, on the other hand, identifies the wide range digital tools available today as a valuable driver of collaboration.

Considering the roots of the BIOEAST Initiative as a policy-science interface, **policy support** is central to HUB operations as well. ToRs mainly refer to the development of bioeconomy strategies and action plans and their alignment with the EU policy environment. Facilitating inter-ministerial discussions is another function the HUBs share, according to BOOST4BIOEAST objectives. Yet, such activities are not mentioned in the Bulgarian, Latvian, and Slovakian ToRs.

R&I support activities are included in almost all ToRs, with activities such as knowledge gathering, knowledge transfer, and exploring funding opportunities. BOOST4BIOEAST-related activities in this regard are centred around the ongoing update of the BIOEAST Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), in which the HUBs play a central role, mapping and representing national priorities.

Capacity building is explicitly mentioned in several ToRs, but typically in rather general terms. Training programs, thematic workshops, and the development of educational materials are among the tools HUBs aim to utilise in this regard. This likely reflects the fact that most HUBs are in the very early stages of developing their organisation. Capacity building efforts are expected to become more pronounced and described in more specific terms in the future. One notable mention is that of the Slovenian ToR, which includes plans for providing mentoring to

NMG leaders, highlighting the importance of internal capacity building that is a crucial element of ensuring the long-term sustainability of the HUBs.

Table 4. HUB Activities

Country	Engagement	Cooperation	Policy Support	R&I Support	Capacity Building
Bulgaria	workshops & annual bioeconomy conferences	dialogue & dispute resolution, networking, cross-sectoral collaboration	strategy & action plan development	knowledge gathering, knowledge exchange	workshops, trainings, educational materials
Croatia	workshops & annual bioeconomy conferences, forums; NMG engagement	cross-sectoral collaboration	strategy & action plan development; inter-ministerial discussions	SRIA update; knowledge gathering, knowledge exchange; Project support	emphasized, not specified
Czechia	emphasized, project-centred	disseminating information; business discovery	strategy development; inter-ministerial discussions	SRIA development; facilitate scale-up & commercialization; knowledge transfer	not specified
Estonia	workshops & annual bioeconomy conferences	inclusive stakeholder-driven initiatives	general advisory role; inter-ministerial discussions	knowledge gathering, knowledge exchange	educational materials
Hungary	workshops & annual bioeconomy conferences; NMG engagement	disseminating information; networking	strategy & action plan development; inter-ministerial discussions	SRIA development; knowledge gathering, knowledge exchange	emphasized, not specified
Latvia	emphasizing inclusivity	diverse membership, networking	national strategy alignment; action plan development	SRIA development; knowledge sharing; funding opportunities	not specified

Table 4. HUB Activities (continued)

Country	Engagement	Cooperation	Policy Support	R&I Support	Capacity Building
Lithuania	workshops & annual bioeconomy conferences; participation in coordination; working groups	disseminating information; inter-institutional dialogue	national strategy alignment; action plan development; inter-ministerial discussions; NCP support	knowledge gathering, knowledge exchange; R&I promotion	seminars, educational materials
Romania	workshops & annual bioeconomy conferences; NMG engagement	dialogue; networking	action plan development; inter-ministerial discussions	SRIA development; knowledge gathering, knowledge exchange; funding opportunities	emphasized, not specified
Slovakia	HUB meetings	disseminating information; business discovery; joint projects	policy advocacy; action plan development	SRIA update; knowledge gathering, knowledge exchange; Open Innovation Challenge	info days; thematic workshops
Slovenia	detailed strategies: inclusivity; clear values; personalisation; interactivity	dialogue; digital tools	national strategy alignment; action plan development; inter-ministerial discussions; NCP support	SRIA development; knowledge exchange; Innovation networks	mentoring NMG leaders

source: own compilation based on HUB ToRs (ToR BG-SI, n.d.)

4 Gaps & Challenges

The comparative review of the HUB ToRs reveals several cross-cutting gaps and challenges that may influence the operational effectiveness and long-term sustainability of national BIOEAST HUBs.

Incomplete ToR Coverage

Despite the successful collection of 10 ToRs, the ToR of the Polish HUB remains unavailable. Its absence limits the completeness of this analysis and constrains regional alignment efforts, especially given Poland's central role in the BIOEAST Initiative. Moreover, the Czech ToR, developed prior to BOOST4BIOEAST, differs from the structure introduced by the HUB Handbook and should be revisited to ensure alignment with project principles.

Variability in Governance and Structure

Although most HUBs are governed by a Coordination Team supported by NMG leaders, there is some notable variability in organizational structures. Some HUBs (e.g., Estonia) lack a dedicated CET, while the governance of others is not clearly described (Czechia, Latvia, Slovakia). Notably, Lithuania opted for a less centralised governing body with wide representation of institutional members, potentially strengthening stakeholder activity.

In their decision-making processes, HUBs strive for consensus in most matters. Nonetheless, the Coordinator or Coordination Team tend to function as the ultimate authority when consensus cannot be reached. Several ToRs also mention voting as a tool for decision making, but such mechanisms are not clearly defined. Overall, a more transparent and specific decision-making structure would better serve HUBs and their members alike.

Gaps in NMGs and TWGs Linkages

Not all HUBs have established NMGs, or thematic structures explicitly aligned with BIOEAST TWGs. This weakens macro-regional coordination and reduces the HUBs' capacity to feed national insights into international dialogues and vice versa. This organisational structure that connects the national and macro-regional levels is crucial for the future operation of BIOEAST and would greatly benefit both sides. On the one hand, NMGs are envisaged to ensure and drive the effective representation of national priorities in macro-regional activities and strategy development, such as the ongoing update of the BIOEAST SRIA. In the other direction, through their liaison with the respective TWG, NMGs could receive timely information on macro-regional and EU-level bioeconomy policies, initiatives, and solutions, facilitating their effective adaptation to the unique local circumstances.

Limited Procedural Clarity

Several ToRs – particularly if developed before the BOOST4BIOEAST project – lack detail on procedural aspects such as membership criteria, decision-making mechanisms, and role definitions. These omissions risk inefficiencies and may undermine stakeholder confidence in HUB governance.

Uneven Activity Implementation Plans

While all HUBs outline ambitious activity portfolios, many ToRs remain vague on implementation details, including timelines, responsible entities, or mechanisms for monitoring progress. Greater specificity would support better planning and allow for more consistent evaluation of HUB performance.

Need for Sustainability Planning

Very few ToRs, with the sole exception of Slovenia, articulate plans for financial sustainability or long-term institutional anchoring beyond the BOOST4BIOEAST project duration. Without such strategies, HUBs may struggle to maintain momentum and stakeholder engagement over time.

These gaps suggest a need for more standardized guidance and support to ensure consistency, alignment, and effectiveness across national HUBs. Harmonizing these elements could strengthen regional cooperation and amplify the impact of the BIOEAST Initiative and the BOOST4BIOEAST project.

5 Conclusions

This deliverable presents a detailed comparison of the ToRs for ten BIOEAST HUBs, developed either under the BOOST4BIOEAST project or earlier initiatives. The analysis focuses on four key elements – objectives, governance, structure, and activities – while evaluating the extent to which each HUB aligns with the conceptual framework outlined in the BIOEAST HUB Handbook.

The assessment demonstrates that the HUBs generally share a strong commitment to advancing national and macro-regional bioeconomy goals. Their ToRs reflect shared principles, such as promoting stakeholder engagement, supporting evidence-based policy, and fostering research and innovation. Nevertheless, the degree of formalization, strategic coherence, and operational detail varies considerably.

Structured HUBs, such as those in Hungary, Lithuania, and Romania, provide strong examples of comprehensive governance, clear strategic direction, and institutional anchoring. These HUBs closely follow the BIOEAST model, integrating TWGs and establishing formal stakeholder roles. Other HUBs, including those in Lithuania and Estonia, emphasize openness and inclusiveness, contributing to broad stakeholder mobilization though often at the cost of procedural clarity.

Older ToRs, such as that of Czechia, may lack the specificity and structural detail needed to ensure sustained impact and regional alignment. The missing Polish ToR remains a notable gap, particularly given Poland's emphasised role in the BIOEAST macro-region.

Several cross-cutting challenges – such as inconsistent TWG-NMG integration, limited sustainability planning, and varied governance practices – suggest a need for additional coordination and support.

To improve future performance and coherence of the HUBs, the following key recommendations are proposed:

- **Harmonize** governance and decision-making structures by promoting the adoption of shared procedural templates and standard roles.
- **Formalize** linkages with TWGs and ensure that NMGs are created or strengthened in all HUBs.
- **Encourage** sustainability planning including financial and institutional strategies for post-project continuity.
- **Facilitate** cross-border exchange through joint HUB events, thematic workshops, and twinning activities.
- **Update & revise** ToRs regularly to reflect evolving national policies and international bioeconomy agendas.

Overall, the HUBs form a strong foundation for continued cooperation in the BIOEAST macro-region. With further refinement and integration, they can serve as lasting platforms for advancing a sustainable and resilient bioeconomy in CEE.

6 References

Martinez de Arano, I. and Arancibia, A. 2024. BIOEAST HUB Handbook. BOOST4BIOEAST project Deliverable 2.1. This deliverable has not been published yet, but available upon request through the BOOST4BIOEAST SharePoint platform.

Terms of Reference of the Bulgarian BIOEAST HUB¹ (ToR BG)

Terms of Reference of the Croatian BIOEAST HUB¹ (ToR CR)

Terms of Reference of the Czech BIOEAST HUB¹ (ToR CZ)

Terms of Reference of the Estonian BIOEAST HUB¹ (ToR EE)

Terms of Reference of the Hungarian BIOEAST HUB¹ (ToR HU)

Terms of Reference of the Latvian BIOEAST HUB¹ (ToR LV)

Terms of Reference of the Lithuanian BIOEAST HUB¹ (ToR LT)

Terms of Reference of the Romanian BIOEAST HUB¹ (ToR RO)

Terms of Reference of the Slovakian BIOEAST HUB¹ (ToR SK)

Terms of Reference of the Slovenian BIOEAST HUB¹ (ToR SI)

¹ ToRs are sensitive, internal documents of the HUBs, therefore these are available upon request through the BOOST4BIOEAST SharePoint platform.

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